

An Investigation of Secondary School Teachers' Job Performance in Relation with Social Support and Work Engagement

Muhammad Ashfaq¹, Syeda Beenish Batool², Rabia Rasheed³

Abstract

This study examines the usefulness and requirement of social support (SS) and work engagement (WE) for boosting secondary school teachers' job performance (JP). Effective teachers enhance the educational system while simultaneously improving student outcomes. The results of the investigation will focus on the necessity and significance of the SS for enhancing SST performance. Additionally, this study will offer several ideas for motivating and assisting teachers. This study was quantitative in nature. Survey method was used to collect the data. 320 SSTs from the City Lahore district made up the sample for this study. Questionnaire was used as the research instrument. It has been concluded that SS and WE positively predicted the JP of SSTs. From the results, it is also concluded that SS statistically significantly predicted the WE of SSTs. Implications were also discussed.

Key Words: Social support, work engagement, job performance, secondary school teachers

1. Introduction

Since it is challenging to recruit enough competent and motivated individuals to the teaching profession, teacher shortages are a concern everywhere in the world. Even when schools discover young, outstanding instructors, it can be challenging to keep them on board because many of them leave because the learning environments do not meet their expectations (Runhaar, 2017). Pakistan is a developing nation, and its development is reliant on how well its educational system performs. Therefore, the teachers' performance must be satisfactory. The quality of education is something that our administration is working to improve using all kinds of material resources. The performance of the secondary school instructors, however, does not meet the necessary requirements despite all these material advantages. Their social and spiritual support, assistance, and active participation in work are required in addition to all the material resources in order to raise the standard of education.

People receive or seek out social support from those in their immediate environment (Papakonstantinou & Papadopoulos, 2010; Ismail et al., 2013). Coworkers, family, friends, and bosses can all provide social support. Kossek, Pichler, Bodner, & Hammer, (2011) claim that social support enables workers to experience and manage the stresses of their jobs. As a result, the purpose of this study is to examine the value and necessity of social support at work.

The level of inspiration and involvement a teacher has in their work is referred to as their level of work engagement (Bakker & Bal, 2010; Klassen et al., 2012). Teachers' engagement has professional, individual, psychological, social, and inspiring effects (Schweitzer, 2014). According to Schweitzer (2014), female teachers exhibit greater levels of work engagement than male teachers. Employees with experience are more engaged than those without it. Male educators are more satisfied and content than female educators in terms of personal and professional development, according to research by Machado-Taylor, White & Gouveia (2014). This is because men have to establish a balance between work and family.

For the country to advance and to improve the standard of education, effective teacher performance is essential. According to Khan, Yusoff, Hussain, & Ismail, (2019) performing a job effectively and efficiently involves using a skill in practice. Effective teaching involves many different factors, including the use of instructional materials, subject comprehension, classroom management, student assessment and evaluation, lesson planning, social and moral development, and the use of information and communication resources (Schaufeli & Salanova, 2011).

Timothy (2018) looked at how employee engagement affects instructors' effectiveness. The researcher discovered a clear and advantageous connection between them. In addition to imparting knowledge or skills to students, a teacher also has the duty to manage, direct, organize, and guide the classroom (Kayisoglu & YUKSEL, 2016). The effectiveness of a teacher in the classroom as a leader has a significant impact on the learning of the kids (Werang, Leba, & Betaubun, (2014). Selamat, Samsu & Kamalu (2013) study found that a teacher's workplace environment has an impact on how well they do their duties.

Ali (2022), Johari, Yean Tan, & Tjik Zulkarnain (2018) discovered that the workload of teachers has an impact on how well they perform at work. It is also mentioned that work-related stressors including workload, a lack of job opportunities, time demands, and student behavior can have an impact on how well instructors accomplish their duties.

Employees' actions, behaviors, and results that are connected to and support organizational goals are referred to as their job performance (Swider & Zimmerman, 2014). Only a few research have specifically looked into the relationships between personality characteristics and involvement in teacher samples. Li, Wang, Gao, and You (2017) discovered, for instance, that Chinese teachers who had a general propensity to take the initiative reported better involvement. Work engagement may have a favorable impact on teachers' involvement because it also

¹ Assistant Professor of Special Education, Department of Special Education, University of Education, Lahore

² Lecturer in Special Education, Department of Special Education, University of Education, Lahore

³ MPhil Scholar, University of Education, Lahore

involves dispositional initiative. Furthermore, for conscientious teachers, increased tenacity may encourage a continued dedication to work-related activities (van Daal, Donche, & De Maeyer, 2014). Extraversion and neuroticism may also be important factors in teacher engagement. Norwegian instructors with higher extraversion and lower neuroticism, as demonstrated by Perera, Granziera, & McIlveen, (2018), had more positive affective experiences.

Pakistan is struggling with a variety of issues, including terrorism, poverty, drug addiction, corruption, and unemployment. Only education can address all of these issues. The success of the entire educational organization depends on the qualified teachers. SST teachers serve a very significant and essential role in secondary school. Future student achievement depends on the SST's successful operation (Suleman & Hussain, 2014). As a transitional step between elementary and higher school, SSTs help pupils get ready for that level of learning. However, in Pakistan, teachers at this level do not perform to the desired level.

This study examines the usefulness and requirement of social support (SS) and work engagement (WE) for boosting secondary school teachers' job performance (JP). Effective teachers enhance the educational system while simultaneously improving student outcomes. The results of the investigation will focus on the necessity and significance of the SS for enhancing SST performance. Additionally, it emphasizes the influence of the mediating variable, or work involvement. Additionally, this study will offer several ideas for motivating and assisting teachers.

Figure 1: The hypothesized research model

Hypothesis

H1: Social support (SS) is the predictor of work engagement (WE) of SSTs

H2: Work engagement (WE) is the predictor of job performance (JP) SSTs.

H3: Social support (SS) is the predictor of job performance (JP) of SSTs.

2. Research Methodology

Subjects

Data was collected from 320 SSTs from City & Shalimar tehsils of Lahore district. There were 160 female teachers (50% of the sample) and 160 male teachers (50% of the sample). eighty six of the participants were M.A B.Ed. (26.9%), ninety five were having MA MEd degree (29.7%), seventy five were having MSc BEd degree (23.4%), forty were MSc MEd (12.5%), and twenty four were Mphil (7.5 %).sample was randomly selected.

2.1. Measures

Section A: Demographic Profile

A series of questions were used to take the demographic information of the teachers i.e, gender, qualification.

Section B: Social Support

Self-developed scale having 10 statements was used. Participants were requested to respond to each item on a 5-point Likert scale.

Section C: Work Engagement

The Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES) was created by Schaufeli and Bakker (2004) and consists of 17 items. It was used to gauge how involved the employees were in their work. Vigor, devotion, and absorption are the three instrument subcategories. It gauges how active, committed, and immersed respondents are in their work. Although the Likert scale has seven points, a five-point scale was used for this survey. Response options included "Never," "Sometimes," "Often," "Mostly," and "Always," with scores ranging from 1 to 5.

Section D: Teachers Job Performance Scale (TJPS)

To evaluate teachers' job performance, we modified a questionnaire from Hanif & Pervz (2004). The teacher version of this 28-item questionnaire was employed. In this questionnaire, four aspects of a teacher's job performance, teaching skill, managerial skill, discipline and regularity, and interpersonal relationship were evaluated.

The questionnaires were validated by the professionals. After validation, research instruments underwent pilot testing. The instrument's social support reliability score was 0.83. The work engagement's instrument had a reliability rating of 0.85. The teacher job performance instrument had a reliability of 0.80.

3. Results

Table 1: Regression analysis of Predictor SS for WE of SSTs

<i>Model</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R²</i>	<i>Adjusted R²</i>	<i>Standard error of estimate</i>	<i>Sig. F change</i>
1	.123	.015	.012	4.03	.027

The table shows that social support as independent variables have a direct, positive and meaningful effect on work engagement as dependent variables. The value of R^2 .015, shows that the independent variables explain 1.5 % variance in the dependent variable which is significant ($p < 0.05$). Here we can say that this model explains significant variation in the work engagement.

Table 2: Regression analysis of predictor work engagement (WE) for job performance (JP) of SSTs

<i>Model</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R²</i>	<i>Adjusted R²</i>	<i>Standard error of estimate</i>	<i>Sig. F change</i>
1	.278	.077	.074	4.38	.000

The table shows that work engagement as independent variables have a direct, positive and meaningful effect on job performance as dependent variables. The value of R^2 .077, shows that the independent variables explain 7.7 % variance in the dependent variable which is significant ($p < 0.05$). Here we can say that this model explains significant variation in the job performance.

Table 3: Regression analysis of Predictor Social Support (SS) for Job Performance (JP) of SSTs.

<i>Model</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R²</i>	<i>Adjusted R²</i>	<i>Standard error of estimate</i>	<i>Sig. F change</i>
1	.390	.152	.149	4.20	.000

The table shows that social support as independent variables have a direct, positive and meaningful effect on job performance as dependent variables. The value of R^2 .152, shows that the independent variables explain 15.2 % variance in the dependent variable which is significant ($p < 0.05$). Here we can say that this model explains significant variation in the work engagement.

Figure 2: Mediation role of social support and work engagement in relation to job performance of SST

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The purpose of the current study is to investigate the significant relationship between the predictor factors (Social Support and Work Engagement) and the outcome variable (Teacher Job Performance). The findings of this study demonstrate a considerable impact of social support on SSTs' job performance. The findings are consistent with research studies carried out by Javadian and Hosseini (2020). The impact of social support on social workers' performance at work was investigated by Javadian & Hosseini (2020). Work performance and social support are positively correlated (Javadian & Hosseini, 2020). Similar to this, Asbari, Novitasari, & Purwanto (2021)

investigate how social support factors affect primary school teachers' performance on the job. The findings of that study demonstrated that all variables have a favorable impact on the performance in Tangerang's five private primary schools. The Novitasari, et al. (2021) study, which found that social support improved teachers' performance, lends credence to the findings of the current study.

The results of the current study demonstrated that work engagement significantly predicted SSTs' job performance. In a similar vein, Kilonzo Were, & Odhiambo (2018) find that work involvement has a favorable impact on the productivity of the Machakos school teachers. The outcome is supported by the Sittar's research efforts as well (2020). According to Sittar's (2020) investigation into the relationship between work engagement and performance among Pakistani university instructors, there is a positive relationship between the two. Another study carried out by the Dajani (2015) demonstrates the outcome. This study found that employee engagement has a significant impact on worker performance but has no impact on employees' commitment to the firm. The findings also show that social support was a favorable predictor of SSTs' work engagement. The research done by Othman et al.,(2021) which supports this study's conclusion. According to the study's findings, job resources—autonomy and support—are connected with employee engagement in the workplace, although performance evaluation is not significantly correlated with it. The association between social support and job performance for secondary school teachers is influenced to some extent by work engagement. The results of Nasuridin, Ling & Khan (2018) provide additional evidence for this conclusion.

It is determined that a cooperative and helpful environment is necessary and favorable for the teachers to function well. It is essential to enhancing teachers' effectiveness. A committee charged with evaluating the school environment should be established by the head teachers. The teachers ought to be encouraging, cooperative, and helpful to one another. It will foster communication between them and their coworkers and encourage the desire to help and support one another. The teachers' performance will be enhanced and improved.

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